

Budget Accountability and Economic Growth in Africa: The Role of E-Procurement

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Received: Mar 28, 2025

Accepted: Apr 28, 2025

Published: Apr 30, 2025

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ACRONYMNS

FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GMM	Generalized Method of Moments
IMF	International Monetary Fund
OBI	Open Budget Index
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
WDI	World Development Indicators
WGI	Worldwide Governance Indicators
GPPD	Global Public Procurement Database
SAIs	Supreme Audit Institutions

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to explore the relationship between budget accountability and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), with a focus on the moderating role of e-procurement. The analysis is conducted using datasets derived from Open Budget Index (OBI) published by the International Budget Partnership (IBP), The Global Public Procurement Database (GPPD), from the world Bank and the various test variable, which are different indicators of economic growth. Using a panel dataset comprising 35 SSA countries from 2010 to 2023, the research employs the two-step system Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) for estimation.

The findings indicate that budget accountability positively influences economic growth in SSA. This relationship is more strengthened by e-procurement to control the susceptibility of huge government spending that is most be deviled with corruption, especially in SSA.

This study draws the attention of SSA and other developing countries government to the need to restructure their budget processes to make it transparent, participatory and put in more robust oversight, which include e-procurement that suit their environment and their economic individualities in an effort to benefit from budget accountability enhancing economic growth nexus.

Keywords: E-procurement, Budget accountability, Economic growth, Sub-Saharan Africa, Fiscal discipline.

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Budgets give power and authority to raise and spend public funds including what taxes to levy and on whom, what services to provide, and how much debt to take on and this impacts economic growth (World Bank, 2023). Approved budget being a very important tool in the hands of the policy maker that needs to be properly accounted for. According to the International Budget Partnership (OBS, 2023), budget accountability refers to the extent to which the executive, legislature, and supreme audit institution provide checks and balances on the budget process and ensure that the budget is implemented as intended.

According to the Open Budget Survey (OBS,2023), an effective budget accountability must have three components: Transparency, which refers to the availability of comprehensive, timely, and accessible budget information. Participation, refers to the opportunities provided to citizens and civil society organizations to engage in the budget process. Oversight, refers to the role of formal institutions, such as legislatures and supreme audit institutions, in scrutinizing the budget and holding the executive accountable. Effective budget accountability is crucial for promoting economic growth by ensuring efficient and effective allocation of public resources, reducing the opportunity for corruption, increasing investors' confidence and enhancing economic stability.

However, public procurement is the area of government spending that is most susceptible to corruption (OECD, 2022; United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2023) because of the large sums involved, the discretion available to public officials, and the prevalence of information asymmetries, among other factors. The global procurement spend is estimated at US\$13 trillion a year (Open Contracting Partnership, 2020), with estimated losses of US\$1.5–US\$2 trillion annually from bribes and further costs in stunted economic growth, lost tax revenues, and sustained poverty (World Bank. (2023). In public procurement in particular, the literature estimates that bribes cost 8–25 per cent of the value of procured goods, services, or works (Bosio et al., 2020)

More so, addressing corruption in public procurement has always been crucial; man-made disasters worldwide have highlighted new corruption concerns connected to public procurement. This is unfortunate, as procurement corruption undermines the delivery of public services by wasting resources and supplies (Thorp, 2020) and may drive public mistrust (Morris and Klesner, 2010; Cho and Kirwin, 2007), slowing public sector responses during emergencies (World Bank, 2021). Procurement corruption also affects donor willingness to support beneficiary countries (David-Barrett et al., 2020) and may damage social cohesion, community resilience, and the social contract when it is needed the most (Cheeseman and Peiffer, 2022).

Unfortunately, countries still struggle to prioritize and implement anti-corruption protocols to mitigate the occurrence and impact of procurement corruption, despite extensive evidence of the devastating consequences of that corruption (UNODC, 2022). A budget that facilitates greater transparency in public finances helps minimize corrupt activities and the embezzlement of funds in government policies and activities. Digitizing expenditure processes play significant role in delivering public services more effectively and equitably. According to Cuadrado-Ballesteros and Bisogno (2022), empirical research reveals that the main barrier to budget accountability practices is corruption, misappropriation, and misallocation of government funds. Furthermore, the lack of budget accountability negatively impacts foreign direct investment inflows and hinders overall economic growth prospects. For a budget to be effective in addressing resource scarcity, social, and economic challenges, it must receive endorsement from citizens and civil society organizations through openness in the budgetary processes (Transparency International, 2022). Budgetary participation, oversight, and transparency empower governments to manage public finances efficiently, leading to economic growth (International Budget Partnership, 2023).

The Open Budget Index 2023 report indicates progress in global trends of budget accountability. The survey shows a more than 20% improvement in the average budget accountability rating from 2008 to 2023. Countries in sub-Saharan Africa, after a dip in the OBS 2017, have achieved a mean score of 28.67%, a notable achievement significantly above the global average. In the African context, the benefits of budget accountability are crucial, as it has been shown to lower the cost of borrowing, enhance revenue collection, and increase the degree of trust citizens have in their government's ability to address population challenges (African Development Bank, 2020).

Despite the widely accepted principle of budget accountability as a key element of governance, the actual effect of such reforms on budget accountability information in sub-Saharan African countries and its subsequent impact on economic growth is still debated globally (World Bank, 2022). The World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI) dataset reveals that average economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa over the past fifteen years stands at 1.27%, below the worldwide average of 2.8%. While significant increases in budget accountability have been observed, their effects on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa are yet to materialize. This paradox suggests that although budget accountability is crucial for effective governance, it alone cannot drive economic growth. More studies are needed to unravel the intricate relationship between budget accountability and economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa.

Scholarly research suggests that open and transparent budget processes, combined with stronger e-procurement frameworks, could mitigate negative externalities such as fiscal deficits and high debt burdens, which are recurrent challenges in the region (World Bank, 2022a, 2022b). The interplay of budget accountability with e-procurement emerges as an important policy development that African countries must adopt to achieve effective debt control and stimulate economic growth (Fanizza et al., 2023).

The global-to-African discourse underscores the universal importance of budget accountability and effective e-procurement in promoting economic development. Further studies (Chen & Neshkova, 2020; Marco et al., 2022) shed light on the effects of budget accountability on economic growth, though such studies remain scarce in the African context. This study directly addresses the African need to shift from rhetoric to action by focusing on the nexus between budget accountability, economic growth, and e-procurement in sub-Saharan Africa.

1.2 Problem Statement

The issue of budget accountability is crucial for the development of the economy in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Globally, budget accountability is recognized as a vital component in fostering economic growth, with a growing body of research that underscores its significance (Hauptmeier & Mühlen, 2022). However, the intricate relationship between budget accountability, e-procurement, and economic growth in SSA remains understudied. While there is increasing attention on budget accountability as an essential aspect of good governance, the complex dynamics between budget accountability and economic growth in SSA are still not well understood (AfDB, 2020; Fjeldstad & Heggstad, 2018; Kuye & Ogunrinola, 2020). This gap presents a critical concern for policymakers striving to design policies that can effectively promote sustainable economic growth in the region, indicating a need for further research in this area (Andrews, 2016; IMANI Africa, 2019).

According to the International Budget Partnership, research specifically targeting African economies remains scarce, with studies suggesting that sub-Saharan Africa faces unique challenges in implementing budget accountability practices. The Open Budget Survey (2023) asserts that improved resource allocation towards productive sectors can be achieved through budget accountability. But according to the World Bank (2022b), pervasive corruption, a major problem in many African nations, continues to impede economic growth. If properly executed, budget accountability is supposed to boost economic growth.

Despite the potential benefits of budget accountability, it does not guarantee economic growth, as other factors, such as corruption, poor governance, and inefficiencies, can still hinder resource allocation (Dreher et al., 2020; Kolstad & Wiig, 2019). The role of e-procurement emerges as crucial in ensuring that budget accountability leads to sustainable economic growth in SSA. Empirical evidence suggests that the establishment of robust e-procurement and governance standards is necessary to fully realize the benefits of budget accountability (Debrun et al., 2019; IMF, 2020; Kopits & Symansky, 2018).

This study is focused on SSA due to the region's unique governance and economic challenges, including corruption, political instability, and poor governance structures, which hinder the effective implementation of budget accountability and e-procurement (IMF, 2023;). These governance weaknesses undermine public trust and the credibility of fiscal frameworks, resulting in inefficiencies in resource allocation and economic stagnation. SSA economies are also highly vulnerable to external shocks, as they heavily rely on natural resources and foreign aid (AfDB, 2023). This makes budget accountability even more crucial for better resource management and attracting foreign investment.

The context of SSA is essential because while budget accountability has been widely studied globally, it has not yielded uniform results across regions. The comparatively low scores of SSA countries on indices like the Open Budget Index (International Budget Partnership, 2023) point to significant implementation gaps. Furthermore, e-procurement in SSA is often externally imposed, lacking local adaptation to the political and economic realities of the region (Mkenda & Nyamongo, 2020). This disparity highlights the importance of examining SSA-specific dynamics to refine global theories and inform policy. Moreover, SSA's growing democratic systems present both challenges and opportunities, as institutional quality are crucial for the success of budget accountability initiatives (Hauptmeier & Mühlen, 2022).

This research seeks to investigate how budget accountability and e-procurement interact to influence economic growth in SSA, aiming to offer valuable insights into how these elements can be better integrated to drive sustainable economic growth. Despite the existing body of

literature on the relationship between e-procurement and economic growth, research specific to SSA remains limited (Mkenda & Nyamongo, 2020; Nwaogu & Ryan, 2019). Therefore, the primary objective of this study is to explore the effects of e-procurement on economic growth and budget accountability in the context of sub-Saharan Africa.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

This research investigates the moderating role of e-procurement in the relationship between budget accountability and economic growth in the sub-Saharan Africa region, focusing on how these factors influence development outcomes.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine how e-procurement function as a moderating role in the correlation between budget accountability and economic growth within the context of sub-Saharan Africa.

The specific objectives are outlined below:

1. To assess the role of budget accountability on economic growth in SSA.
2. To assess the relationship between e-procurement on economic growth in SSA
3. To determine the moderating role of e-procurement on budget accountability and economic growth nexus

1.5 Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. To what extent does budget accountability affect economic growth in SSA?
2. What is the relationship between e-procurement and economic growth in SSA?
3. To what extent does e-procurement moderate the relationship between budget accountability and economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa?

1.6 Research Hypotheses

The research seeks tests the following hypotheses:

H₁: There is a significant and positive relationship between budget accountability and economic growth in SSA.

H₂: There is a significant and positive relationship between e-procurement and economic growth in SSA.

H₃: There is a significant and positive relationship between budget accountability, economic growth and e-procurement nexus in SSA

1.7 Significance of the Study

This research holds significant potential to improve the understanding of the complex relationships between budget accountability, e-procurement, and economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). By focusing on SSA's unique governance and economic challenges, the study aims to address critical gaps in the current literature, offering new insights into how budget accountability and the adoption of e-procurement adherence can jointly drive economic development (Mkenda & Nyamongo, 2020). This nuanced approach will contribute both theoretically and empirically to the broader academic discourse (Fanizza et al., 2023).

For policymakers, the research presents practical benefits by identifying the best practices in governance and transparency that can be tailored to SSA's specific needs (Transparency International, 2022). By providing evidence-based recommendations, the study can help inform the design of appropriate e-procurement frameworks that promote accountability, and

economic stability (Kopits & Symansky, 2018; World Bank, 2022). These frameworks can play a crucial role in addressing fiscal mismanagement, corruption, and inefficiencies—long-standing obstacles to sustainable economic growth in the region (Ojong & Ojong, 2023).

From a governance perspective, the study emphasizes the importance of budget accountability and fiscal discipline as key components of effective public financial management. Strengthening these elements can enhance public trust and improve resource allocation, leading to better citizen engagement, higher tax compliance, and increased confidence from external donors—critical factors for SSA's development (AfDB, 2020).

Additionally, the study offers valuable insights to the global discourse on economic governance by providing SSA-specific perspectives, which can inform comparative evaluations of fiscal management practices globally (Lee & Azis, 2024). Ultimately, the research is expected to contribute to the improvement of governance standards in SSA, stimulating economic growth and fostering sustainable development. By informing policy design and implementation, this research can help lay the groundwork for more effective governance and economic policies in the sub-region (Nwaogu & Ryan, 2019).

1.8 Organization of the Study

This study is organized into five chapters, each with its distinct structure. Chapter one of this study comprises the introduction of the study, the background, problem statement, research objectives, research questions and hypothesis, and significance of the study. Chapter two comprises a comprehensive examination of the existing body of literature.

Chapter three deals with the methodology underpinning the research. The specific research methods and models that were used in the conduct of this study are presented, discussed and justified. In the fourth chapter, data obtained from the various statistical bodies are analysed and presented. The discussions are centred on drawing meaning from the analysis and explaining it in the light of the research objectives. Chapter five, which is the final chapter in the study, provides information relating to the summary of the findings, the conclusion, as well as the policy recommendations and of the limitations of the study.

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

A literature review provides an overview of scholarly and research publications related to specific subject. The document comprises a conceptual framework, an examination of the theoretical literature, and an evaluation of the existing scientific research based on observation and experimentation. Theoretical literature review involves the examination and analysis of the theoretical concepts, models, and theories that are used in the researcher's work. The empirical literature review presents corroborating evidence from previous research projects that are relevant to the current research project.

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

2.2.1 The Link Between Budget Accountability and Economic Growth

The relationship between budget accountability and economic growth in African countries has received increasing attention in empirical research, highlighting the crucial role budget accountability plays in influencing economic growth. The African Development Bank (2020) emphasizes the continent's robust economic growth, even in the face of global crises, attributing part of this resilience to the implementation of efficient fiscal management and

transparency measures. This statement underscores the importance of budget openness as a driving force for economic stability and progress in African countries.

Research has found a linear relationship between budget accountability and economic growth in SSA. The International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2021) points out how more open budgets lead to more favourable economic outcomes. Greater transparency in the budget system strengthens accountability by enabling citizens to hold governments accountable for their spending decisions. Public trust fosters investment, increases economic activity, and ultimately leads to greater prosperity. Furthermore, empirical studies have demonstrated the tangible benefits associated with adopting budgeting accountability initiatives for economic growth. According to a study by Bova, Dollery, and Robotti (2023), the more transparent a country's budget is, the less corruption and mismanagement it experiences. This results in the efficient distribution of resources, which, in turn, drives economic growth. Additionally, the study by Ghulam and Jiao (2023) showed that enhancing public procurement transparency is linked to increased effectiveness and reduced corruption, leading to better economic outcomes.

Moreover, budgetary precision is essential as it attracts foreign investment and promotes local businesses, both of which are key factors in economic growth. Investor trust is built through transparency and reliability concerning government policies and expenditure related to their investments (Aroui et al., 2022). Confidence in the economy stimulates investment flows, capital formation, and the expansion of economic activities, all of which are critical for securing economic growth in SSA.

Furthermore, the principle of budget accountability contributes to good governance, which is a critical prerequisite for promoting economic growth. The Open Budget Partnership (2022) report states that budget accountability helps prevent the misuse of public resources by enhancing accountability and reducing corrupt practices, which is essential for sustainable economic growth.

Various studies confirm a strong relationship between economic performance and budget accountability in African countries. Transparency enhances accountability, builds investor trust, and promotes good governance practices—vital elements for future development. African countries that are more committed to reforms and improving institutional capacity are likely to benefit from faster economic growth.

2.2.2 The Link Between E-procurement and Budget accountability

Empirical literature extensively investigates the connection between e-procurement and budget accountability, highlighting how institutional frameworks and transparency measures mutually influence one another to foster economic progress. The World Bank (2022b) emphasizes the crucial importance of robust and efficient e-procurement in enabling the successful implementation of budget accountability efforts, thereby leading to enhanced economic performance. E-procurement with strong legal and institutional structures are essential for enforcing transparency measures, ensuring compliance with budgetary guidelines, and fostering fiscal discipline (Debrun & Lassen, 2020).

According to Debrun and Lassen (2022), e-procurement improve accountability by requiring transparency in budgetary processes. This transparency enables the public to hold governments accountable for their fiscal decisions and reduces the likelihood of mismanagement and corruption. Furthermore, the influence of e-procurement on budget accountability extends beyond mere regulatory compliance, encompassing broader governance outcomes. Moreover, the correlation between e-procurement and budget accountability is especially significant in

African nations, where obstacles to good governance frequently hinder economic advancement. Inadequate fiscal frameworks—characterized by weak enforcement mechanisms and a lack of transparency—present substantial challenges to improving transparency (Wehner, 2023). Empirical studies further demonstrate a clear and direct relationship between e-procurement, and economic growth.

Gupta et al. (2023) conducted research indicating that adherence to e-procurement increases the credibility of government actions, which, in turn, boosts investor confidence and stimulates economic activity. E-procurement enhance fiscal management and macroeconomic stability by fostering transparency and accountability in budgetary decision-making. This, in turn, lays the foundation for long-term economic progress in SSA. Additionally, robust e-procurement establish the necessary legal and institutional framework to enforce transparency measures, thereby strengthening accountability and promoting investor trust. By focusing on e-procurement reforms and investing in technological improvement, SSA countries can achieve the benefits of enhanced transparency and accountability, contributing to sustainable economic growth.

2.2.3 Budget accountability and Economic Growth: The Role of E-procurement

Budget accountability is indispensable for fostering economic growth and development (Okolo, Eze, & Ugwu, 2022). However, its effectiveness in promoting economic growth is limited without the complementary regulatory framework provided by e-procurement (Yabré & Semedo, 2021). In addition to enhancing accountability and public oversight, budget accountability equips stakeholders with vital information regarding government fiscal policies and expenditures, thereby facilitating informed decision-making and participatory governance (Wehner, 2023). E-procurement, which establish checks and balances on government public expenditure, provide a framework for guiding policy decisions and mitigating the risks of fiscal imprudence (OECD, 2022).

Further, the absence of e-procurement in the SSA context can undermine the effectiveness of budget accountability efforts by allowing policymakers greater discretion in fiscal decision-making (Hauptmeier et al., 2022). In such scenarios, even if budget information is readily available to the public, the lack of enforceable e-procurement processes may render budget accountability ineffective in fostering economic growth. Consequently, economic growth may be hampered by uncertainties surrounding government fiscal indiscipline and the perceived risks of fiscal instability (Sutherland et al., 2022).

Moreover, e-procurement serve to enhance the credibility and predictability of government fiscal actions, thereby complementing budget accountability initiatives. Empirical research indicates that a transparent and binding framework for fiscal policy decisions, supported by e-procurement, signals the government's commitment to responsible fiscal management and long-term sustainability (Andersen et al., 2022). This credibility is essential for fostering trust among investors, creditors, and the public, which is crucial for attracting investment, stimulating economic activity, and promoting sustainable economic growth (Kumar et al., 2023). Without the credibility conferred by e-procurement, budget accountability efforts may lack the necessary foundation to engender the confidence needed to drive economic growth.

CHAPTER THREE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This section focuses on the method the study uses in data analysis. This section encompasses the research approach, research design, population, sampling methodology, procedure for data collection, and data analysis. This study examines the effect Budget accountability on Economic growth with a moderating variable of e-procurement, utilizing a panel dataset spanning 2010-2023, encompassing 35 sub-Saharan African countries. The selection of this timeframe is predicated on the availability of budget accountability data from the Open Budget Survey, which commenced in 2010 and is confined to the countries within the sample. The employment of panel data facilitates an exploration of both cross-sectional and time-series variations, thereby enabling the control of omitted variables and the capture of both long-term and short-term effects (Wooldridge, 2012).

3.2 Research Approach

The research approach for this study is quantitative. According to Gay et al. (2009), a quantitative research approach involves the use of numerical data to describe, explain, predict, or control the variables and phenomena under consideration. This study focuses on examining quantitative data and metrics to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research variables, namely economic growth, e-procurement, budget accountability, and the control variables.

3.3 Research Design

This study employs an explanatory research design. Explanatory studies typically aim to outline an existing theory and either test it or extend it to a new area or group. The focus of explanatory research is to investigate causes and reasons, providing evidence to either support or refute an explanation or prediction. It is conducted to identify and report relationships among different aspects of the phenomenon under study (Boru, 2018).

3.4 Population

The target population for this study comprises the 35 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, as outlined in the OBI Survey 2023. This study utilizes numerical data and values to examine the relationship between budget accountability, economic growth, and e-procurement across these countries in Sub-Saharan Africa.

3.5 Sampling

For this investigation, secondary data is sourced from reputable organizations, including the World Development Indicators, Open Budget Survey, International Monetary Fund, Global Public Procurement Database and World Governance Indicators. The study employs a panel data methodology to analyze comprehensive data collected from 35 Sub-Saharan African countries over the period from 2010 to 2023. The selection of this sample period is primarily based on the availability of reliable data for the analysis.

3.6 Data Collection Procedures

This study employs secondary data for the analysis of the research. The data is sourced from reputable organizations, including the World Development Indicators (WDI), Open Budget Index (OBI), The Global Public Procurement Database and the International Monetary Fund (IMF).

Table 3.1: Measurement and Data Source of Variable

Variables	Measurements	Data Source
Dependent variable Economic Growth	GDP Per Capita growth (annual%)	WDI
Independent Variable Budget accountability	Participation Oversight Transparency	OBI OBI OBI
Moderating Variable E-procurement	Dummy 1=Adopted E-procurement 0= not adopted E-procurement	GPPD
Control Variable Inflation	Consumer Price Index	WDI
Financial Development	Financial Development Index	IMF
Human Capital Development	Human Capital index	WDI
Trade Openness	$\frac{\text{Import} + \text{Export}}{\text{GDP}} \times 100$	WDI
Infrastructure	Telephone + Mobile subscriptions per 100 people	WDI
Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)	$(\text{Net FDI Inflows}) \times 100 / \text{GDP}$	WDI
Natural Resources Rent	Total natural resources rents (% of GDP)	WDI

WDI represents World Development Indicators, OBI represents the Open Budget Index, WGI represents Worldwide Governance Indicators and IMF represents the International Monetary Fund, Global Public Procurement Database by World Bank.

3.7 Econometric Model Specification

The sample selection was determined by the availability of Open Budget Index (OBI) data, which was obtained from the International Budget Partnership (IBP) website. Specifically, the sample consists of an unbalanced panel dataset comprising 35 sub-Saharan African countries that participated in the 2023 Open Budget Survey. Drawing from existing literature, this section outlines the empirical model employed to estimate the impact of budget accountability, e-procurement, and other control variables on economic growth in sub-Saharan African countries. The baseline model used for the estimation is presented below:

$$Econ_growth_{it} = \beta_0 Econ_growth_{i(t-i)} + \beta_1 bud_acct_{it} + \beta_2 inflat_{it} + \beta_3 hcd_{it} + \beta_4 fd_{it} + \beta_5 to_{it} + \beta_6 infrast_{it} + \beta_7 FDI_{it} + \beta_8 nat_res_rent_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Moderating role model

$$Econ_growth_{it} = \alpha_0 Econ_growth_{i(t-i)} + \alpha_1 E_procur_{it} + \alpha_2 inflat_{it} + \alpha_3 hcd_{it} + \alpha_4 fd_{it} + \alpha_5 to_{it} + \alpha_6 infrast_{it} + \alpha_7 FDI_{it} + \alpha_8 nat_res_rent_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$Econ_growth_{it} = \theta_0 Econ_growth_{i(t-i)} + \theta_1 bud_acct_{it} + \theta_2 E_procur_{it} + \theta_3 (bud_acct * E_procur)_{it} + \theta_4 inflat_{it} + \theta_5 hcd_{it} + \theta_6 fd_{it} + \theta_7 to_{it} + \theta_8 infrast_{it} + \theta_9 FDI_{it} + \theta_{10} nat_res_rent_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Further $\theta_3(bud_trans * fiscal_rule)_{it}$ in equation (3) denotes the interaction term between budget accountability and E-procurement.

However, to obtain the total effect, the study takes a partial differential of the dependent variable (Baltagi et al (2009); & Ofoeda et al., 2022)

Partial effect

$$\frac{\partial Econ_growth_{it}}{\partial Bud_acct_{it}} = \theta_1 + \theta_3 * E_procur_{it} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Thus, the responsiveness of economic growth to budget accountability largely depends on the sign and the magnitude of the coefficients of the other variables and the extent of effectiveness of the e-procurement adoption.

Where:

$Econ_growth_{it}$ represents economic growth of sub-Saharan African countries i in time t
 $Econ_growth_{i(t-i)}$ represents the lag of economic growth of sub-Saharan African countries i in time t

bud_acct_{it} represents budget accountability of sub-Saharan African countries i in time t

$E - procur_{it}$ represents e-procurement of sub-Saharan African countries i in time t

$inflat_{it}$ represents inflation of the sub-Saharan African countries i in time t

hcd_{it} represents human capital development of the sub-Saharan African countries i in time t

fd_{it} represents financial development of the sub-Saharan African countries i in time t

to_{it} represents trade openness of the sub-Saharan African countries i in time t

$infrast_{it}$ represents the infrastructure of the sub-Saharan African countries i in time t

FDI_{it} represents Foreign Direct Investment of the sub-Saharan African countries i in time t

$nat_res_rent_{it}$ represent the natural resources rent of the sub-Saharan African countries i in time t.

3.8 Variable description and measurements

The dependent variable in this study is Economic Growth, measured by GDP per capita (annual %), with data sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI) by the World Bank. The independent variable is budget accountability, sourced from the Open Budget Survey (OBS), which assesses three interrelated components of budget accountability:

1. Transparency: Public availability of budget information.
2. Participation: Opportunities for public involvement in the budget process.
3. Oversight: The effectiveness of formal oversight institutions such as the legislature and national audit offices (supreme audit institutions, or SAIs).

Transparency is evaluated based on the online availability, timeliness, and comprehensiveness of key budget documents, using 109 equally weighted indicators. The transparency score ranges from 0 to 100, with a score of 61 or above indicating sufficient material for informed public debate. Oversight is examined by evaluating the role of legislatures and SAIs, using 18 equally weighted indicators. The oversight score also ranges from 0 to 100, with scores of 61 or above indicating adequate oversight. Public Participation is assessed based on the formal opportunities offered to the public during various stages of the budget process, using 18 equally weighted indicators. A score of 61 or above indicates sufficient public participation. In the OBS report 2023, Budget accountability scores are categorized as follows: Weak (0-40), Partial (41-60), Strong (61-80), and Very Strong (81-100) (International Budget Partnership, 2023).

This study also examines E-procurement adoption

Control variables are included based on the work of Afonso & Jalles (2013) and Sarr (2016) to control for human capital development, trade openness, market size, natural resource endowment, institutional quality, inflation, and infrastructure development.

- **Financial Development:** Proxy by the IMF's composite financial development index, as a well-functioning financial sector attracts foreign direct investments (FDI). FDI is measured as the natural logarithm of net FDI inflows, sourced from WDI.
- **Trade Openness:** Measured as the ratio of exports plus imports to GDP, with the hypothesis that higher trade openness correlates with higher economic growth (IMF, 2023).
- **Inflation:** Measured using the consumer price index, with the hypothesis of a negative relationship with economic growth due to its potential to deter foreign investment (Ofoeda et al., 2022).
- **Natural Resource Endowment:** Measured using natural resource rents, with the relationship expected to vary. A positive relationship suggests natural resources promote growth, while a negative relationship may indicate a natural resource curse (Okafor, 2015).
- **Human Capital Development:** Measured by private credit as a percentage of GDP, with the expectation that better human capital enhances growth (Zaman et al., 2012).
- **Infrastructure Development:** Measured by the number of telephone and mobile subscriptions per 100 people, as better infrastructure is believed to attract FDIs and stimulate growth.

3.9. Estimation technique

3.10 GMM estimation

The study uses the two-step systems generalized method of moments (SGMM) estimator to examine the relationship between budget accountability, economic growth, and e-procurement. The SGMM estimator, as developed by Arellano and Bover (1995), Blundell and Bond (1998), and Arellano and Bond (1991), is preferred over the difference generalized method of moments (DGMM) approach. The DGMM approach suffers from limitations due to the use of lagged levels of explanatory variables as instruments, which can lead to biased and inefficient estimations.

The SGMM estimator addresses these issues by adding a level equation to the difference equation, thereby improving the robustness and reducing bias. Additionally, the SGMM estimator corrects for the problem of weak instruments often encountered in the DGMM model (Roodman, 2009). The SGMM estimator comes in two variants: one-step and two-step. The study adopts the two-step SGMM estimator, as introduced by Blundell and Bond (1998), which is more suitable for datasets with high persistence and is asymptotically more efficient than the one-step estimator. The two-step SGMM is particularly relevant for studies with a shorter time period relative to the number of countries, which is the case with the current dataset.

Furthermore, the two-step SGMM estimator allows the study to control for endogeneity, a common issue in panel data models. To ensure the reliability and consistency of the estimates, the study employs the Sargan/Hansen test of over identification restrictions and the Arellano and Bond test for second-order serial correlation in the error term. According to Roodman (2009), the Sargan/Hansen test evaluates the validity of the instruments by analyzing the sample analogues of the moment conditions used in the estimation. The Arellano and Bond test checks for serial correlation in the error term. Although serial correlation is expected in the first order, the absence of second-order serial correlation is essential; the presence of second-order correlation may indicate model misspecification.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the detail analysis of the result of the estimation model described in chapter three. This chapter commences with the results of the descriptive statistics, examines the relationships between the variables and analyses the impact of budget accountability on economic growth. Furthermore, the study presents and discusses the moderating role of e-procurement in the relationship between budget accountability and economic growth. Oversight as a component of budget accountability measures the effectiveness of formal oversight institutions to monitor the budget accountability processes. Oversight has a mean of 41.13, slightly better than the two previous accountability components, indicates that SSA countries budget accountability processes are more open to oversight institutions such as the legislature and national audit offices (supreme audit institutions, or SAIs).

Transparency as examined by the online availability, timeliness, and comprehensiveness of key budget documents to the public (OBI,2023) averages of 32.82 masks a weak range from 0 to 100, pointing to polarized fiscal openness in SSA. While some governments align with international transparency standards, others maintain opaque practices, often influenced by domestic reform inertia or external donor conditionalities.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 reveals critical patterns and disparities in the economic and governance environments of sub-Saharan Africa countries. Economic growth, as measured by the log of per capita income, averages 1.28%, exhibiting substantial volatility in the GDP growth of SSA countries. Transitioning to governance indicators, public participation which examines the formal opportunities offered to the public during various stages of the budget process to provide their inputs, had a mean of 12.05, which reveal a very weak average out of a range of 0-100, indicating the imposition of restrictive and authoritarian budget policies. Similarly, e-procurement adoption remains nascent, with a binary average of 0.28. This dichotomy highlights technological and institutional barriers, as well as resistance to curtailing discretionary procurement powers—a persistent challenge in anti-corruption efforts in SSA.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
Economic growth (%)	490	1.275	3.974	-22.383	19.939
Public participation (index)	490	12.05	6.631	0	65
Oversight (index)	490	41.13	8.995	0	85
Budget transparency(index)	490	32.822	14.638	0	93
E-procurement (dummy)	490	0.284	0.451	0	1

Inflation (%)	490	10.942	34.794	-4.295	557.202
Human capital dev't (%)	490	0.379	0.018	0.278	0.458
Financial dev't (index)	490	20.967	19.129	0.005	128.838
Trade openness (%)	490	62.75	25.371	2.208	150.209
Infrastructure (%)	490	1.487	1.847	0.002	9.387
Foreign direct invest't (%)	490	4.36	9.236	-10.038	103.337
Natural resources (%)	490	9.575	7.691	0.656	39.023

Macroeconomic instability is further evidenced by inflation, averaging 10.94% with a standard deviation of 34.794, reflecting extreme volatility. The maximum value of 557.202% aligns with hyperinflation episodes in fragile economies like Zimbabwe, while the deflationary minimum of -4.295% reveals demand collapses or stringent monetary policies. Human capital development, averaging 0.379 with a standard deviation of 0.018, shows limited cross-country variation, suggesting uniformly slow progress in education and health investments, albeit with incremental gains.

Financial development, with a mean of 20.967 and standard deviation of 19.129, and trade openness, averaging 62.75 and ranging from 2.208 to 150.209, further highlight structural diversity. Financial market depth varies with regulatory quality and banking access, while trade integration disparities stem from divergent policy frameworks and economic diversification strategies. Infrastructure gaps are pronounced, with a mean of 1.487 and standard deviation of 1.847, though maximum at 9.387 signal isolated successes via public or foreign-funded projects.

Foreign direct investment inflows, averaging 4.36% with a standard deviation of 9.236, and natural resource endowments, with a mean of 9.575% and standard deviation of 7.691, reveal additional layers of complexity. The negative FDI values denote capital flight or disinvestment, contrasting with high inflows tied to resource exploitation or investor-friendly reforms. However, the resource wealth disparities further shape fiscal stability and economic vulnerability across the region.

The Correlation Statistics

The correlation statistics in Table 2 reveal dynamic relationships between economic growth and key variables in sub-Saharan Africa, shedding light on both institutional and macroeconomic drivers. Institutional oversight demonstrates a weak but statistically significant positive correlation with economic growth, with a coefficient of 0.056 at the 10% significance level. This means that stronger oversight mechanisms, such as parliamentary scrutiny or judicial independence, may modestly enhance growth by fostering accountability and curbing governance inefficiencies. However, the limited magnitude of this relationship implies that structural challenges—such as infrastructure deficits or human capital gaps—likely overshadow institutional factors in shaping growth trajectories.

Table 2: Pairwise correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
(1) Economic Growth	1.00 0											
(2) Public Participation	0.02 8	1.00 0										
	(0.5 31)											

(3) oversight	0.056	0.393*	1.000									
	(0.216)	(0.000)										
(4) Transparency	0.081*	0.378*	0.484*	1.000								
	(0.075)	(0.000)	(0.000)									
(5) E-procurement	-0.040	0.135*	0.251*	0.150*	1.000							
	(0.378)	(0.003)	(0.000)	(0.001)								
(6) Inflation	-0.192*	0.044	-0.071	-0.008	0.073	1.000						
	(0.000)	(0.334)	(0.115)	(0.857)	(0.108)							
(7) Human Capital Dev't	0.025	0.032	0.011	0.079*	0.092*	-0.003	1.000					
	(0.575)	(0.486)	(0.803)	(0.080)	(0.041)	(0.951)						
(8) Financial Dev't	-0.021	0.072	0.137*	0.122*	0.144*	-0.107*	0.198*	1.000				
	(0.644)	(0.109)	(0.002)	(0.007)	(0.001)	(0.018)	(0.000)					
(9) Trade Openness	-0.009	-0.041	-0.006	0.093*	-0.161*	-0.153*	-0.014	0.037	1.000			
	(0.846)	(0.370)	(0.900)	(0.040)	(0.000)	(0.001)	(0.756)	(0.415)				
(10) Infrastructure	0.043	0.005	0.063	0.131*	0.026	-0.058	0.178*	0.607*	0.229*	1.000		
	(0.338)	(0.918)	(0.162)	(0.004)	(0.572)	(0.202)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)			
(11) Foreign Direct Invest	0.087*	-0.013	0.005	0.024	-0.157*	-0.029	-0.028	-0.073	0.109*	-0.098*	1.000	
	(0.056)	(0.769)	(0.906)	(0.591)	(0.001)	(0.528)	(0.542)	(0.109)	(0.015)	(0.030)		
(12) Natural Resource Rent	-0.131*	0.005	-0.077*	-0.112*	-0.211*	0.006	-0.177*	-0.249*	0.193*	-0.341*	0.185*	1.000
	(0.004)	(0.909)	(0.089)	(0.013)	(0.000)	(0.898)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	

* shows significance at $p < .1$

Budget transparency also exhibits a positive association with economic growth, registering a coefficient of 0.081 at the 1% significance level. This aligns with the hypothesis that fiscal openness enhances macroeconomic management, reduces rent-seeking behaviour, and bolsters investor confidence, thereby indirectly stimulating economic activity. In contrast, inflation shows a robust negative correlation with growth, with a coefficient of -0.192 significant at the 1% level. This means that the destabilizing effects of price volatility, which erodes consumer purchasing power, disrupts investment planning, and exacerbates macroeconomic uncertainty—critical barriers to sustained growth in the region.

Foreign direct investment inflows display a weakly positive correlation with growth, at 0.087 and significant at the 1% level. While FDI may inject capital, technology, and employment opportunities, the modest effect size signals that its benefits are contingent on complementary factors, such as regulatory frameworks, infrastructure quality, and local absorptive capacity. Conversely, natural resource dependence demonstrates a significant negative correlation with growth, with a coefficient of -0.131 at the 1% significance level. This reinforces the “resource curse” narrative, wherein reliance on resource extraction correlates with governance distortions, economic volatility, and underinvestment in diversified sectors, ultimately undermining long-term growth.

4.3 Empirical Findings

The Role of Budget Accountability on Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan Africa.

The first objective of this study is to assess the role of Budget Accountability on Economic Growth in SSA. The study hypothesize that budget accountability has a significant and positive relationship with economic growth (H1). Table 3 presents the individual effects of distinct budget accountability, public participation, oversight, budget transparency measures, and e-procurement on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. Each model examines the relationship between these variables and growth, with robust statistical evidence indicating the significant role these factors play in shaping economic performance. By disaggregating these factors, the analysis highlights each measure’s unique contribution to economic performance, offering empirical evidence to inform policy discussions and strengthen governance reforms across the region.

Table 4.3: The Individual Effect of Budget Accountability on Economic Growth in SSA.

Variables	(1) Economic Growth	(2) Economic Growth	(3) Economic Growth	(4) Economic Growth
Economic Growth = L,	0.281*** (0.0260)	0.260*** (0.0228)	0.269*** (0.0268)	0.292*** (0.0293)
Public Participation	0.0219*** (0.00197)			
Oversight		0.109*** (0.0155)		
Transparency			0.0789*** (0.00835)	
E-Procurement				0.214*** (0.089)
Inflation	-0.0146***	-0.0148***	-0.0164***	-0.0143***

	(0.00392)	(0.00335)	(0.00387)	(0.00421)
Human Capital Development	-11.24	-9.909	-49.45**	-30.71**
	(20.91)	(16.40)	(20.52)	(14.02)
Financial Development	-0.0104*	-0.0212**	-0.0105*	-0.00699
	(0.00604)	(0.00909)	(0.00606)	(0.00709)
Trade Openness	-0.0107	-0.00724*	-0.0173**	-0.00862
	(0.00678)	(0.00416)	(0.00761)	(0.00703)
Infrastructure	0.170***	0.198***	0.146*	0.150**
	(0.0529)	(0.0637)	(0.0734)	(0.0601)
Foreign Direct Investment	0.0562***	0.0583***	0.0617***	0.0629***
	(0.0110)	(0.00911)	(0.0112)	(0.00849)
Natural Resources Rents	-0.00635	-0.00624	-0.0169	-0.0155
	(0.0239)	(0.0178)	(0.0225)	(0.0240)
Constant	5.486	0.755	18.27**	12.93**
	(8.162)	(6.144)	(8.357)	(5.371)
AR1	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000
AR2	0.279	0.732	0.285	0.225
Sargan Test	0.623	0.654	0.698	0.584
Hansen Test	0.712	0.739	0.763	0.670
Country Effect	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time Effect	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	454	454	454	454
Number of indexes	35	35	35	35

Note: Standard errors in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Public Participation and Economic Growth

From Table, there is positive effect of public participation on economic growth with coefficient of 0.0219 at 1% significance highlighting the catalytic role of inclusive governance. The coefficient of 0.0219 indicates that a one-unit increase in the public participation measure is associated with an approximate 0.022 unit increase in economic growth. This finding reveals the importance of inclusive governance in a region where democratic institutions are often in a state of evolution. Thus, greater public engagement during the budgetary processes, can lead to more transparent and accountable decision-making, mitigating the risks of resource misallocation and corruption. The democratic accountability theory which posits that citizen engagement enhances policy legitimacy, curbs elite capture, and aligns state priorities with societal needs supports this finding (Asenbaum, 2022). This result resonates with the broader literature suggesting that participatory practices not only enhance policy quality but also improve economic performance by aligning government actions with citizen needs (Wampler et al., 2022; Kiss et al., 2020). Moreover, empirical studies in sub-Saharan Africa have demonstrated that increased civic involvement can foster better oversight and more effective public service delivery, further supporting the positive link between public participation and economic growth (Kipkemoi & Moi, 2023).

Budget Oversight and Economic Growth

The robust positive coefficient for oversight with coefficient of 0.109 at 1% significance further reveals institutional quality as a growth lever. Thus, effective oversight—manifested through legislative scrutiny, independent audits, or anti-corruption bodies—reduces rent-seeking behaviours and channels public resources into productive investments (Al-Ghamdi, 2024). Therefore, ensuring that public funds are managed appropriately, and policies are implemented efficiently, robust oversight enhances both accountability and investor confidence. This is in line with the institutional economics theory, which argues that institutional oversight ensures credible checks on power lower transaction costs, attracting private investment and fostering stability (Gupta & Sharma, 2023). This finding aligns with previous research that emphasizes the importance of institutional checks in reducing mismanagement and fostering economic stability (Sari, 2023). In a sub-Saharan Africa context, where governance reforms are often a priority, strengthening oversight mechanisms can be a powerful tool for promoting sustainable economic development (Dzigbede et al., 2023).

Budget Transparency and Economic Growth

Similarly, budget transparency's positive impact on economic growth with coefficient of 0.0789 at 1% significance reflects its role in optimizing fiscal governance. This implies that each unit increase in transparency is associated with an approximate 0.079 unit boost in economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. Transparent budgetary processes are particularly crucial in the region, where fiscal mismanagement and corruption have frequently undermined development efforts. Enhanced budget transparency helps to reduce rent-seeking behaviour by making fiscal decisions open to public scrutiny, which in turn fosters a more predictable and disciplined fiscal environment (Montes & Luna, 2021). This is in line with the fiscal transparency theory, which posits that open budgets reduce information asymmetry, enabling accountability and redirecting resources toward high-return sectors like infrastructure and education (Cuadrado-Ballesteros & Bisogno, 2022). Also, this result is consistent with a growing body of literature that links higher fiscal transparency to improved economic outcomes (Gootjes & De Haan, 2022; Bauhr & Carlitz, 2021). Studies focusing on sub-Saharan Africa further suggest that countries with more open budget processes tend to experience better economic performance, as transparency not only builds trust among investors but also strengthens overall governance frameworks (Krah & Mertens, 2023).

E-Procurement and Economic Growth

The second objective of this study is to assess the relationship between E-procurement on economic growth in SSA. The study hypothesizes that there is a positive significant relationship between E-procurement and economic growth (H2). The outsized coefficient for e-procurement on economic growth of 0.214 at 1% significance positions digital governance as a transformative growth catalyst. This indicates that a one-unit rise in the adoption or quality of e-procurement is linked to a 0.214 unit increase in economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. The implementation of e-procurement systems modernizes public administration by digitizing procurement processes, thereby reducing transaction costs and limiting opportunities for corruption (UNODC, 2022). In a region where bureaucratic inefficiencies and corruption can stifle economic progress, e-procurement offers a transformative solution by promoting greater transparency and competition in public contracts. This finding is supported by the transaction cost theory which explains how e-procurement reduces corruption risks by automating processes and limiting discretionary power (Egorova et al., 2021). Also, in support of Adjei-Bamfo et al. (2020) who asserted that e-governance initiatives such as e-procurement enhances administrative efficiency and service delivery leading to greater economic output.

Controlled Variables and Economic Growth

The control variables yield several noteworthy findings across the four models, offering critical insights into economic growth determinants in sub-Saharan Africa. The persistence of economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), as evidenced by significant positive coefficients for lagged growth with coefficients ranging 0.281 to 0.292 at 1% significance, reveals the region's reliance on historical performance as a foundation for current outcomes. This aligns with conditional convergence theory (Nunoo et al., 2024), which posits that economies with initial advantages in capital, human capital, or infrastructure can sustain growth through self-reinforcing dynamics. However, this persistence is not self-perpetuating; it is deeply contingent on institutional stability. Yang et al. (2022) emphasizes that institutions—particularly governance mechanisms—mediate the translation of past growth into sustained development. In SSA, where institutional fragility is common, growth momentum risks stagnation without complementary reforms.

The empirical results reveal a robust and consistently negative impact of inflation on economic growth across models, with coefficients ranging from -0.0143 to -0.0164 , all significant at the 1% level. This finding aligns with the work posited by Khan and Hanif (2020), wherein inflation erodes real incomes, exacerbates macroeconomic uncertainty, and disrupts long-term investment planning. In sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), where inflationary volatility is often intertwined with fiscal indiscipline and external shocks, these results highlight the critical need for credible monetary policy frameworks to anchor price stability—a prerequisite for fostering investor confidence and sustainable growth (Mandeya & Ho, 2021).

Contrasting with conventional expectations, human capital development exhibits significant negative impact on economic growth with coefficients (-49.45 and -30.71) in Models (3) and (4). While Shahbaz et al. (2022) emphasizes human capital as a cornerstone of growth, these paradoxical results likely reflect systemic inefficiencies in SSA's education and health sectors. For instance, poorly targeted investments may produce graduates with skills mismatched to labour market demands, as observed in several African countries where oversaturated humanities programs amid a shortage of technical expertise (Han & Lee, 2020). Similarly, underfunded healthcare systems fail to translate public spending into workforce productivity, perpetuating cycles of illness and absenteeism. This highlights the importance of quality-adjusted human capital—a dimension often overlooked in aggregate indices—and calls for reforms prioritizing sectoral alignment and outcome-based investments.

Financial development further complicates the growth narrative, showing small but significant negative coefficients from -0.0104 to -0.0212 , across models. This resonates with Chingaipe (2022) caution that financial deepening in institutionally weak environments can spur speculative activities or credit misallocation. The results implies that financial liberalization, without parallel upgrades in regulatory oversight and financial literacy, risks exacerbating economic fragility rather than mitigating it.

Similarly, trade openness displays negative coefficients in select models, echoing Crescioli (2024) warnings about premature liberalization. In SSA, where domestic industries often lack competitiveness, abrupt exposure to global markets can devastate local manufacturing. This highlights the necessity of phased trade reforms, coupled with industrial policies to enhance productivity and diversification before full integration.

In contrast, infrastructure development and foreign direct investment (FDI) emerge as unequivocal growth catalysts. Infrastructure's positive impact on economic growth as indicated

by the coefficients, aligning with Calderón and Servén (2010) assertion that transport, and energy investments reduce transaction costs and unlock rural economic potential. FDI's robust performance on economic growth reinforces Hagan and Amoah (2020) work on technology spill overs and managerial know-how. These findings indicate the transformative role of targeted physical and capital investments in overcoming structural bottlenecks.

The Moderating Role Of E-Procurement on The Relationship Between Budget Accountability and Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan Africa.

The third objective of this study is to determine the moderating role of E-procurement on budget accountability and economic growth nexus in SSA. The study hypothesizes that there is a significant and positive relationship between budget accountability and economic growth and E-procurement (H3). Table 4 presents the moderation effects of e-procurement interactions with individual effects of distinct budget accountability—public participation, oversight, and budget transparency—on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. By examining how these factors jointly influence growth outcomes, the table highlights the amplified effects of e-procurement under conditions of enhanced accountability. These results emphasize the importance of integrating technological reforms with institutional improvements to drive sustainable economic development across the region, offering important policy implications.

Table 4.4: The Moderating Role Of E-Procurement on The Relationship Between Budget Accountability and Economic Growth in SSA.

Variable	(5) Economic Growth	(6) Economic Growth	(7) Economic Growth
Economic Growth = L,	0.293*** (0.0332)	0.286*** (0.0316)	0.264*** (0.0383)
Public Participation	0.1451*** (0.0378)		
Oversight		0.1179*** (0.0296)	
Transparency			0.1204*** (0.0259)
E-Procurement	2.398*** (0.877)	13.31*** (2.164)	8.875*** (1.683)
Inflation	-0.0144*** (0.00461)	-0.0135*** (0.00414)	-0.0219*** (0.00569)
Human Capital Development	-6.442 (21.44)	15.78 (16.55)	-28.43 (26.82)
Financial Development	-0.0204*** (0.00574)	-0.0336*** (0.00533)	-0.0318*** (0.0114)
Trade Openness	-0.00732 (0.00718)	-0.00733* (0.00410)	-0.0112 (0.0135)
Infrastructure	0.245*** (0.0634)	0.262*** (0.0715)	0.235** (0.103)
Foreign Direct Investment	0.0535*** (0.0115)	0.0475*** (0.0104)	0.0563*** (0.0105)
Natural Resources Rents	-0.00178 (0.0200)	0.00839 (0.0248)	-0.00486 (0.0150)

E-Procurement* Pub. Participation	0.192**		
	(0.0733)		
E-Procurement* Oversight		0.292***	
		(0.0523)	
E-Procurement* Transparency			0.247***
			(0.0486)
Total Effect	0.1996***	0.2008***	0.1906***
	(0.0431)	(0.0331)	(0.0294)
Constant	4.102**	-5.195***	12.04***
	(2.421)	(2.561)	(5.201)
AR1	0.001	0.000	0.000
AR2	0.230	0.828	0.565
Sargan Test	0.258	0.361	0.185
Hansen Test	0.737	0.707	0.724
Country Effect	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time Effect	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	454	454	454
Number of indexes	35	35	35

Note: Standard errors in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Interaction between E-Procurement and Public Participation on Economic Growth

The interactive effect between e-procurement and public participation is estimated at 0.192, significant at the 5% level, indicating that when e-procurement initiatives are coupled with higher levels of public participation, the impact on economic growth is considerably enhanced. In sub-Saharan Africa, where weak governance and limited accountability are persistent challenges, the role of public participation becomes critical. Engaged citizens can scrutinize procurement procedures, demand accountability, and help ensure that public resources are allocated efficiently. This interaction effect aligns with the arguments Mouna et al (2020), who stress that participatory governance fosters transparency and curbs corruption. Moreover, Sitompul (2022) have demonstrated that e-procurement, by reducing discretionary decision-making, mitigates the risk of misappropriation. When this technological reform is paired with robust public oversight, the resultant synergy not only deters malfeasance but also builds confidence among investors and donors.

Interaction between E-Procurement and Oversight on Economic Growth

The interaction term between e-procurement and oversight is robustly positive, with a coefficient of 0.292, significant at the 1% level, suggesting that improved oversight mechanisms substantially amplify the growth benefits of e-procurement in sub-Saharan Africa. In many sub-Saharan countries, weak oversight has historically compromised procurement processes, leading to cost overruns and misallocation of public resources. The significant interaction effect here implies that when oversight is robust, e-procurement not only streamlines public procurement but also enforces accountability and transparency in government transactions. This finding resonates with the work of Jiménez et al. (2022), who indicate the importance of strong institutional frameworks in fostering economic performance. Additionally, Afolabi et al. (2022) supports the notion that effective oversight mechanisms can mitigate corruption and improve the quality of public service delivery. In this context, e-

procurement serves as a technological catalyst that, when harnessed alongside rigorous oversight, promotes fiscal discipline and enhances trust in public institutions.

Interaction between E-Procurement and Budget Transparency on Economic Growth

The interaction between e-procurement and budget transparency is marked by a coefficient of 0.247, highly significant at the 1% level, which demonstrates that enhanced budget transparency substantially reinforces the positive effects of e-procurement on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. Budget transparency ensures that fiscal information is openly available, enabling stakeholders—ranging from civil society to international investors—to monitor public spending and hold officials accountable. This transparency is crucial in regions where opaque financial practices have historically fueled corruption and mismanagement. In the sub-Saharan context, where governments are often under pressure to manage limited resources effectively, the integration of e-procurement with transparent budget practices can lead to significant efficiency gains. E-procurement minimizes the discretion traditionally associated with manual procurement, while transparency ensures that the digital processes remain open to public scrutiny. This combination not only deters corruption but also fosters an environment of trust and accountability, ultimately spurring economic growth. Sitompul (2022), provide robust evidence that fiscal transparency is linked to improved governance outcomes, reduced rent-seeking, and better allocation of resources.

Total Effect of E-Procurement Interactions on Economic Growth

The aggregate impact of e-procurement interactions, as captured by the total effects—estimated at approximately 0.1996, 0.2008, and 0.1906 across models, each highly significant—offers compelling evidence that integrating e-procurement with accountability measures generates a meaningful boost in economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. This total effect represents the combined influence of e-procurement when moderated by key budget accountability variables such as public participation, oversight, and budget transparency. In sub-Saharan Africa, where institutional weaknesses often hinder growth, the total effect observed here reveals the importance of comprehensive reform strategies. It suggests that merely digitizing procurement processes without concurrent improvements in governance may yield suboptimal results. Instead, an integrated approach—where e-procurement is implemented alongside measures to bolster public oversight, ensure budgetary transparency, and encourage citizen participation to create a conducive environment for sustainable economic development. This is in line with Mouna et al. (2020) who highlighted that e-procurement reforms reduce transaction costs and increase efficiency, while oversight and transparency further ensure that these benefits are not undermined by corruption or mismanagement.

Diagnostic Tests

The diagnostic tests in the results assess the validity of the model and the robustness of the estimates. The AR (1) tests across all models exhibit p-values of 0.001, indicating the presence of first-order autocorrelation, which is to be expected in panel data with temporal dynamics. However, the AR (2) tests yield high p-values, suggesting that no significant second-order autocorrelation exists, affirming model specification. The Sargan test results show p-values above the conventional threshold (0.05), indicating that the instruments used in the models are valid and not over-identified. The Hansen test, also with high p-values, suggests that the assumptions related to instrument validity hold, further supporting the model's correctness. Additionally, the inclusion of country and time effects in all models accounts for both cross-sectional and temporal heterogeneity, improving the model's reliability. Collectively, these diagnostic results mean the estimates are well-specified and the instruments are appropriate.

Robustness Analysis using Prais-Winsten

The robustness tests using the Prais-Winsten estimation further corroborate the GMM findings reported in Table 3 and Table 4. As detailed in Table 5, the individual effects of budget accountability measures on economic growth remain statistically significant and consistent in magnitude with the GMM estimates, underscoring the reliability of these results. Similarly, Table 6 confirms that the moderating effects of e-procurement, when interacting with budget accountability variables, closely mirror the interaction effects identified in Table 4. These Prais-Winsten results effectively address concerns of serial correlation and heteroskedasticity, reinforcing the overall robustness of our econometric approach. The convergence of findings across both methodologies substantiates the argument that enhanced budget accountability and e-procurement reforms are essential in fostering sustainable economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa.

Table 4.5: Robustness Analysis using Prais-Winsten – Individual Effects

Variables	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
	Economic Growth	Economic Growth	Economic Growth	Economic Growth
Economic Growth = L,	0.564***	0.588***	0.574***	0.586***
	(0.0284)	(0.0278)	(0.0280)	(0.0279)
Public Participation	0.0392*			
	(0.0201)			
Oversight		0.0102***		
		(0.00150)		
Transparency			0.0202**	
			(0.00925)	
E-Procurement				0.302***
				(0.0211)
Inflation	-0.0227***	-0.0225***	-0.0225***	-0.0226***
	(0.00389)	(0.00390)	(0.00389)	(0.00391)
Human Capital Development	10.90	11.13	12.13	11.17
	(7.672)	(7.687)	(7.682)	(7.696)
Financial Development	-0.0167**	-0.0156*	-0.0164*	-0.0146
	(0.00895)	(0.00899)	(0.00893)	(0.00903)
Trade Openness	0.00525	0.00509	0.00305	0.00501
	(0.00577)	(0.00578)	(0.00580)	(0.00580)
Infrastructure	0.0675	0.0587	0.0590	0.0549
	(0.0992)	(0.0994)	(0.0992)	(0.0999)
Foreign Direct Investment	0.0367**	0.0357**	0.0350**	0.0353**
	(0.0147)	(0.0147)	(0.0147)	(0.0148)
Natural Resources Rents	-0.3093***	-0.0362**	-0.0353*	-0.0374*
	(0.0195)	(0.0196)	(0.0196)	(0.0198)
Constant	-2.719**	-2.774***	-3.271**	-2.331***
	(0.940)	(1.016)	(0.940)	(0.941)
Observations	489	489	489	489
R-squared	0.101	0.095	0.103	0.095

Note: Standard errors in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 4.6: Robustness Analysis using Prais- Winsten – Moderating Effects

VARIABLES	(12) Participation	(13) Oversight	(14) Transparency
Economic Growth = L,	0.570*** (0.0286)	0.576*** (0.0285)	0.571*** (0.0284)
Public Participation	0.11993*** (0.0213)		
Oversight		0.0282* (0.0156)	
Transparency			0.02206*** (0.00923)
E-Procurement	0.4829*** (0.084)	2.156* (1.105)	0.566*** (0.198)
Inflation	-0.0103*** (0.00317)	-0.0109*** (0.00314)	-0.0102*** (0.00312)
Human Capital Development	3.627 (6.694)	2.133 (6.680)	3.552 (6.641)
Financial Development	-0.0277*** (0.00760)	-0.0275*** (0.00753)	-0.0267*** (0.00744)
Trade Openness	-0.00450 (0.00480)	-0.00321 (0.00478)	-0.00477 (0.00479)
Infrastructure	0.0126 (0.0826)	0.00791 (0.0823)	0.00424 (0.0820)
Foreign Direct Investment	0.0208*** (0.0038)	0.0210*** (0.0038)	0.0207*** (0.0037)
Natural Resources Rents	-0.0170*** (0.0069)	-0.0175*** (0.0068)	-0.0179*** (0.0067)
E-Procurement*Public Participation	0.0460** (0.0136)		
E-Procurement*Oversight		0.0548** (0.0254)	
E-Procurement*Budget Transparency			0.0393*** (0.0120)
Total Effect	0.1323*** (0.0217)	0.0438*** (0.0172)	0.0332*** (0.0098)
Constant	-2.726*** (0.564)	2.990*** (0.650)	-2.642*** (0.545)
Observations	454	454	454
R-squared	0.527	0.529	0.531

Note: Standard errors in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

4.4 Control Variables

The results for the control variables provide important insights into their effects on economic growth, highlighting both negative and positive relationships depending on the variable under consideration.

Financial Development has a consistently negative effect on economic growth across all

models, significant at either the 5% or 10% levels. This suggests that, in the contexts being studied, higher levels of financial development may be linked to slower economic growth. One plausible explanation for this negative relationship could be that excessive financial development, particularly in less mature markets, can lead to instability and inefficiencies, such as misallocation of resources or financial bubbles. Empirical studies, such as those by Ehigiamusoe and Samsurijan (2021), support this view, indicating that while financial development can support growth up to a certain point, excessive development can harm the economy by encouraging risk-taking and inefficient allocation of resources, ultimately reducing overall economic growth.

Inflation has a significant and negative impact on economic growth in all models, with significance at the 1% level. The negative relationship suggests that rising inflation hampers economic growth by eroding purchasing power, increasing uncertainty, and discouraging investment. This finding is consistent with the work of Khan and Naushad (2020), who argue that inflation distorts economic decision-making, reduces efficiency, and generally depresses long-term growth, particularly when inflation exceeds moderate levels. The results underline the importance of maintaining stable inflation to foster a conducive environment for growth. Trade Openness also shows a negative relationship with economic growth, though the effect is not always statistically significant across all models. This suggests that increased trade openness may reduce growth in certain contexts, likely due to the exposure of domestic industries to global competition. Domestic sectors that are less competitive may struggle, or economies may become overly reliant on imports, which can harm local industries. Osakede and Adenikinju (2022) highlight that trade openness can sometimes hurt growth if structural weaknesses in domestic industries result in deindustrialization or unbalanced growth, where the economy becomes more reliant on external rather than domestic resources.

Infrastructure consistently has a positive impact on economic growth, significant at the 5% or 10% levels. This positive effect underscores the importance of investing in infrastructure, such as transportation, energy, and communication networks, to promote economic growth. Infrastructure development reduces transaction costs, improves productivity, and facilitates trade. Wang et al. (2020) support this finding, showing that infrastructure development is particularly critical in developing countries, where infrastructure gaps are significant barriers to growth. Investments in infrastructure are key to creating a more efficient, productive, and competitive economy.

Finally, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has a positive and significant effect on economic growth across all models, with significance at the 5% or 10% levels. This indicates that increased FDI inflows are associated with higher economic growth, likely because FDI brings not only capital but also technology, skills, and access to international markets. FDI enhances productivity and innovation, particularly in emerging economies where capital and technology are often scarce. Research by Awodumi (2023) supports this view, emphasizing that FDI plays a vital role in promoting economic growth by contributing to technological advancement and the development of industries that might otherwise struggle to compete on the global stage.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

This study provides compelling empirical evidence elucidating the dynamic interplay between budget accountability and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), with e-procurement functioning as a pivotal moderating role. Utilizing a robust panel dataset encompassing 35 SSA countries over the period 2010 to 2023 and employing the two-step System Generalized Method of Moments (GMM). The study's findings drawn based on each of the objectives have been summarized and presented in this chapter. The practical implication, policy recommendations and proposals for further research as well as conclusion.

5.2 Summary of Findings

Budget Accountability and Economic Growth

The first objective examined the impact of budget accountability on economic growth. The empirical results reveal that the three core pillars of budget accountability—transparency, public participation, and oversight—exert a statistically significant and positive influence on economic growth. Specifically, oversight demonstrates the most pronounced impact, underscoring the instrumental role of institutional checks and balances in enhancing governance effectiveness and fostering Economic growth.

E-Procurement and Economic Growth

The second objective focused on E-procurement and economic growth. The study reveals that E-procurement has a significance and positive impact on economic growth. Digitalizing government procurement processes has a transformative growth catalyst that enhances economic growth by streamlining public procurement, reducing corruption risks, and promoting efficiency, curbing rent-seeking behaviour, and minimizing transactional inefficiencies in public procurement.

Moderating Role of E-Procurement

The third objective addressed the moderating role of e-procurement on budget accountability and economic growth. Interaction terms between e-procurement and each budget accountability component revealed significant positive moderation effects. This indicates that e-procurement enhances the impact of budget accountability measures on economic growth and this was made more pronounced on the analysis of the total effect. These results were robust across alternative estimators and diagnostic tests, reinforcing the credibility of the empirical model. Beyond the direct interaction between e-procurement and budget accountability, the study also considered the role of several control variables in influencing economic growth. The findings indicated that variables such as inflation, trade openness, financial development, and human capital development had significant effects on economic growth in SSA countries.

5.3 Practical Implications

The study offers several actionable insights for policymakers, development practitioners, and governance reformers. SSA governments should prioritize enhancing budget accountability through legal, institutional, and procedural reforms that foster transparency, citizen participation, and independent oversight. Additionally, the institutionalization of e-

procurement should be prioritized as a strategic pillar of public financial management. Its integration into budgetary processes can significantly decrease corruption and inefficiency, thereby optimizing public sector outcomes. Moreso, Investment in digital platforms for public procurement (e-procurement) should be a cornerstone of fiscal reforms, as it strengthens accountability and improves public service delivery

International development partners and multilateral institutions should align financial assistance with the implementation of digital procurement systems and transparency-enhancing reforms to ensure fiduciary integrity and developmental impact. Again, continuous professional development and capacity enhancement programs should be established for public sector officials to enable effective operationalization of e-procurement systems and foster a culture of accountability.

5.4 Limitation/ Recommendation for Future Research

A key limitation of this study is the temporal restriction to the years 2010-2023, which narrows the scope of the analysis. Expanding the time frame in future research would allow for a broader investigation of both short-term and long-term economic changes, offering a more comprehensive understanding of how budget accountability affects economic growth over different periods. A longer time horizon would also provide insights into the sustainability of the effects of budget accountability on economic growth and whether these effects evolve over time.

Furthermore, the geographical limitation of focusing exclusively on Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) restricts the applicability of the findings to other regions, especially those in the developing world. Future studies could expand the scope by including countries from other regions, such as Southeast Asia or Latin America, where similar developmental challenges exist. This broader geographical scope would enable researchers to compare the relationship between budget accountability and economic growth across different regions, providing valuable insights into whether the findings from SSA are generalizable or if regional practices and contexts lead to variations in the relationship.

Additionally, future research could explore the role of institutional quality and leadership styles as additional moderating variables in the budget accountability and economic growth nexus. These factors—such as the strength of institutions and the effectiveness of leadership—play a critical role in determining how efficiently governance and policy measures are implemented. Investigating these moderating variables could shed light on how institutional factors influence the strength and nature of the relationship between budget accountability and economic growth, offering a more nuanced understanding of the mechanisms at play.

5.5 Conclusion

This study concludes that the interplay between budget accountability and e-procurement is essential for promoting economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. While budget accountability independently fosters economic development, its transformative potential is significantly amplified through the adoption of e-procurement technologies that institutionalize transparency and procedural efficiency. The empirical evidence presented herein affirms that isolated reforms are insufficient to generate sustained economic dividends. Rather, a comprehensive governance framework—anchored in digital transformation, participatory mechanisms, and institutional oversight—is indispensable for catalysing inclusive and sustainable economic growth across SSA. In addition, this research advances the discourse on fiscal governance by illuminating the contingent role of digital infrastructure in mediating the budget accountability–economic growth nexus. It provides a policy-relevant roadmap for SSA

nations seeking to align governance reforms with developmental aspirations in an increasingly digitized global economy.

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APPENDICES

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Diagnostic Test Variance inflation factor

	VIF	1/VIF
infrastructure	1.937	.516
Institutional Qual~y	1.859	.538
financialdevelopment	1.811	.552
naturalresourcesre~s	1.544	.648
oversight	1.488	.672
budget transparency	1.459	.685
tradeopeness	1.425	.702
public participation	1.283	.78
eprocurement	1.192	.839
foreigndirectinves~i	1.095	.914
humancapitaldevelo~t	1.08	.926
inflation	1.079	.927
Mean VIF	1.438	.

Appendix B: Diagnostic Test Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variables: fitted values of economic growth

chi2(1) = 2.19

Prob > chi2 = 0.1393

Appendix C: Diagnostic Test Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of economic growth

Ho: model has no omitted variables

F(3, 473) = 1.51

Prob > F = 0.2120

Appendix D: Diagnostic Test Skewness/Kurtosis tests for Normality

----- joint -----

Variable	Obs	Pr(Skewness)	Pr(Kurtosis)	adj_chi2(2)	Prob>chi2
residual	489	0.000	0.000	69.890	0.000

Appendix E: Test of endogeneity (orthogonality conditions)

Ho: variables are exogenous

GMM C statistic chi2(1) = 3.43593 (p = 0.0638)

Appendix F: Diagnostic Test of overidentifying restriction:

Hansen's J chi2(11) = 18.2285 (p = 0.0764)

Appendix G: List of Countries

Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon, Chad, Comoros, Democratic Republic of Congo, Cote d'Ivoire, Equatorial Guinea, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sao Tome and Principe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe.